

Study on Qualification of Sugarcane Bagasse Ash in Partial Cement Replacement in Concrete

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Abstract

This study investigates the strength performance of concrete using partial blends of cement and sugarcane bagasse ash (SCBA). The bagasse was dried under sunlight and burnt in air. SCBA was obtained after passing the residual through 200 μ m sieve. Elemental analysis was conducted on SCBA and Ordinary Portland Land cement (OPC) by EDXRF (Energy Dispersive X-ray Fluorescence) technique to evaluate its percentage composition. These were then used to replace OPC by weight in ratio of 0%,5%,10%,20%,30% and 40% in concrete grade (M-15 &M-20). Twelve pieces of 150 mm concrete cubes were prepared. These cubes were tested 28 days of curing ages and then density, maximum load and compressive strength of cubes were determined respectively. To investigate the pozzolanic behavior of SCBA, grade M-20 (95%OPC+5%SCBA) and (90% OPC+10% SCBA) concrete crushes were analyzed by XRD analysis.

Keywords: bagasse ash, pozzolanic, compressive strength, concrete

Introduction

There are some important factors that encourage this research works. Agriculture sector in Myanmar is the main industry in the country and sugarcane is also the main crop. Sugarcane, an industrial raw material is principally grown mostly in Mandalay and Bago Regions as well as Mon, Kachin, Shan and Rakhine State in Myanmar round about one million tons of sugarcane are produced yearly in Myanmar. Agricultural wastes are widely available, renewable and virtually free and they are important resources. Researchers all over the world today are focusing on ways of utilizing either industrial or agricultural waste, as a source of raw materials for industry. Agricultural wastes are converted into heat, steam, charcoal, methanol ethanol, bio diesel as well as raw materials (animal's feed, composting, energy and biogas construction etc.). The production of energy from agricultural waste has been utilized to varying degrees in different parts of the world. This waste, utilization would not only be economical, foreign exchange earnings and environmental pollution control [V. S. Aigbodion et al, 2010]. Industrial wastes, such as blast furnace slag, fly ash and silica fume are being used as supplementary cement replacement materials. Sugarcane is a member of grass family and tree-free renewable resource and one of the most important agricultural plants that grown in dry regions. Bagasse is a by-product from sugar industries which is burnt to generate power required for different activities in the factory [Mini Vishwakarma, et al, 2015]. Bagasse is the matted cellulose fiber residue from sugarcane that has been processed in a sugar mill. Previously, bagasse was burnt as a means of solid waste disposal. However, as the cost of fuel oil, natural gas, and electricity has increased, bagasse has come to be regarded as a fuel rather than refuse in the sugar mills. The chemical compositions of this product are cellulosic fibers, water and some soil soluble materials such as cube sugar, by passing time cube sugar is converted alcohol also the evaporation of bagasse fiber produce the methane gas which can cause fire in some circumstance [Osinubi.K.J et al, 2007]. Bagasse is also used as a raw material for paper making due to its fibrous content and about 0.3 tons of paper can be made from one ton of bagasse [Juan H Sosa Arnao et al, 2004]. The bagasse is used in the energy production (steam/electricity), fuel, hydrolysis, paper pulp, cellulose and wood veneer. [S.B Hassan et al, 2010]. Currently, there has been an attempt to utilize the large amount of bagasse ash, the residue from an in-line sugar industry and the bagasse-biomass fuel in electric

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generation industry. When bagasse is burned under controlled conditions, it also gives ash having amorphous silica, which has pozzolanic properties [R.Srinivasan and K.Sathiya, 2010]. Pozzolan is a siliceous or siliceous and aluminous material, which in itself possesses little or no cementitious value but will, in finely divided form and in the presence of moisture, chemically react with calcium hydroxide Ca(OH)_2 to form compounds possessing hydraulic cementitious properties. Ordinary Portland Cement is the most extensively used construction material in the world. Since the early 1980s, there has been an enormous demand for the mineral admixture and in future this demand is expected to increase even more. If some of raw material having similar composition can be replaced by weight of cement in concrete then cost could be reduced without affecting its quality. For this reason sugarcane bagasse ash (SCBA) is one of the main byproduct can be used as mineral admixture due to its high content in silica (SiO_2). Also in this modern age every structure has its own intended purpose and hence to meet this purpose modification in traditional cement concrete has become essential. This situation has led to the extensive research on concrete resulting in mineral admixture to be partly used as cement replacement to increase workability in most structural application. [Mrs.U.R.Kawade et al, 2013]. Concrete is a composite material composed of coarse aggregate bonded together with fluid cement that hardens over time. Most concrete used is lime-based concrete such as Portland cement concrete or concrete made with other hydraulic cements, such as ciment fondu. When aggregate is mixed together with dry Portland cement and water, the mixture forms a fluid mass that is easily moulded into shape. The cement reacts chemically with the water and other ingredients to form a hard matrix that binds the material together into a durable stone-like material that has many uses [Zongjin Li 2011].

Experimental Procedure

Sample Preparation

The sugarcane was collected from Eain Mae Township, Ayeyawaddy Region Myanmar and shown in figure 1. The sugarcane waste, bagasse was dried under sunlight to reduce the moisture content in bagasse shown in figure 2. The dry bagasse was burnt in air and produced the gray color sugarcane bagasse ash, SCBA shown in figure 3 and 4 was obtained. SCBA was then sieved with a 200 μm standard sieve and purified SCBA was obtained. SCBA and OPC were analyzed by (Energy Dispersive X-ray Fluorescence) EDXRF technique, to evaluate their chemical composition. By observing the EDXRF results, the chemical composition of SCBA and OPC were determined. For concrete cubes sample preparation, the main ingredients are Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC), sugarcane bagasse ash, SCBA, sand, coarse aggregates and water were shown in figure 5,6,. In this experimental work, twelve 150mm concrete cubes, grade M-15 (1:2:4) and grade M-20 (1:1.5:3) were designed. Based upon the quantities of ingredient of the mixes, OPC (replacing cement by 0% SCBA) concrete cube, which is regarded as “sample 1” and 5%,10%,20%,30% and 40% replacing cement concrete cubes which were marked out as sample 2,3,4,5 and 6 were prepared for concrete grade M-15 and M-20 respectively. The ingredients of concrete were thoroughly mixed in pan and while mixing the ingredient of concrete, water which was used to form concrete paste was shown in figure 7. Water to cement ratio (w/c) was different for different specimens and then uniform thoroughly consistency concrete paste was achieved and concrete specimens were casted by using the plastic mould as shown in figure 8,9 and 10. These concrete cubes were produced for 28 day- curing age as shown in figure 11. These were tested by compression machine, the density, maximum load and compressive strength of concrete cubes was determined as

shown in figure 12, 13 and 14. Concrete crushes M-20 (95%OPC+5%SCBA) and (90%OPC+10% SCBA) were analyzed by XRD analysis to investigate the pozzolanic behavior of SCBA and symmetric representation of concrete cubes were shown in figure 15. For sample preparation, SCBA, cement, sand and coarse aggregates weight ratio for concrete cubes were shown in table (1) and (2).

Table 1 Cement, SCBA, sand, coarse aggregates and water to cement weight ratio for grade M-15 concrete

Table 2 Cement, SCBA, sand, coarse aggregates and water to cement weight ratio for grade M-20 concrete

Sample No.	Cement (%) (1)	Sand (2)	Coarse Aggregates (4)	Sugarcane bagasse ash (SCBA)(%)	Total Weight	Water to Cement Ratio, w/c
Sample(1)	1kg (100%)	2 kg	4 kg	0 kg (0%)	7 kg	0.5 (0.5)kg
Sample(2)	0.95 kg (95%)	2 kg	4 kg	0.05kg (5%)	7 kg	0.6 (0.6)kg
Sample(3)	0.9kg (90%)	2 kg	4 kg	0.1kg (10%)	7 kg	0.6 (0.6)kg
Sample(4)	0.8kg (80%)	2 kg	4 kg	0.2kg (20%)	7 kg	0.65 (0.65)kg
Sample(5)	0.7kg (70%)	2 kg	4 kg	0.3kg (30%)	7 kg	0.75 (0.75)kg
Sample(6)	0.6kg (60%)	2 kg	4 kg	0.4kg (40%)	7 kg	0.85 (0.85)kg

Sample No.	Cement (%) (1)	Sand (1.5)	Coarse Aggregates (3)	Sugarcane bagasse ash (SCBA) (%) (Primary state)	Total Weight	Water to Cement Ratio (w/c)
Sample(1)	1.27kg (100%)	1.9 kg	3.81 kg	0 kg (0%)	6.98 kg	0.35 (0.44)kg
Sample(2)	1.21 kg (95%)	1.9 kg	3.81 kg	0.06kg (5%)	6.98 kg	0.4 (0.51)kg
Sample(3)	1.14kg (90%)	1.9 kg	3.81 kg	0.13kg (10%)	6.98 kg	0.4 (0.51)kg
Sample(4)	1.02kg (80%)	1.9 kg	3.81 kg	0.25kg (20%)	6.98 kg	0.55 (0.69)kg
Sample(5)	0.89kg (70%)	1.9 kg	3.81 kg	0.38kg (30%)	6.98 kg	0.65 (0.83)kg
Sample(6)	0.76kg (60%)	1.9 kg	3.81 kg	0.51kg (40%)	6.98 kg	0.65 (0.83)kg

Fig 13 Weigh out the specimen

Fig 14 Measuring compressive strength of concrete cube

Fig 7 Concrete paste

Fig 8 Concrete paste pour in mould

Fig 9 Concrete cast

Fig 10 Concrete cubes

Fig 11 Curing concrete cubes

Fig 12 Measuring the dimension of specimen

Fig 1 Sugarcane from Eain Mae Township

Fig. 2 The dry Bagasse

Fig 3 The dry Bagasse was burnt in air

Fig 4 The grey color Bagasse ash

Results and Discussion

EDXRF Analysis

The chemical composition of sugarcane bagasse ash, SCBA and Ordinary Portland Cement, OPC determined by EDXRF analysis were shown in table (3, and 4). The chemical composition of SCBA illustrates that it contains high amount of silicon (Si) as dominant element and the second dominant elements are potassium (K), calcium (Ca), zinc (Zn) and iron (Fe) in addition to small amount of manganese (Mn), titanium (Ti), rubidium (Rb), strontium (Sr), copper (Cu) and yttrium (Y). By observing the EDXRF analysis of chemical composition of OPC, it was found that calcium (Ca) is the most dominant element and silicon (Si) and Iron (Fe) are second dominant elements. Small amount of elements potassium (K), sulfur (S), titanium (Ti), strontium (Sr), zinc (Zn), manganese (Mn), arsenic (Ar), zirconium (Zr) and molybdenum (Mo) are also contained in OPC.

Table 3 Chemical composition of sugarcane bagasse ash, SCBA by EDXRF analysis

Components	Si	K	Ca	Zn	Fe	Mn	Ti	Rb	Sr	Cu	Y
SCBA	33.75	28.39	18.28	9.03	7.35	1.45	0.95	0.33	0.22	0.2	0.02
	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%

Table 4 Chemical composition of ordinary portland cement, OPC by EDXRF analysis

Components	Ca	Si	Fe	K	S	Ti	Sr	Zn	Mn	As	Zr	Mo
OPC	82.97	6.86	5.874	1.91	1.65	0.37	0.16	0.06	0.05	0.04	0.03	0.02
	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%

XRD analysis of grade M-20 (95%OPC+5%SCBA) and (90% OPC+10% SCBA) concrete crushes

In this research, an XRD analysis is used to investigate the pozzolanic behavior of the SCBA and to identify the hydration products formed during the hydration of OPC in concrete making is shown in figure 16 and 17. By observing the XRD patterns of grade M-20 (95%OPC+5%SCBA) and (90% OPC+10% SCBA) concrete crushes curing age of 28 days, it was found that calcium silicate hydrate, C-S-H, calcite, CaCO_3 and calcium hydroxide, $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ peaks were observed in both patterns. The most intense C-S-H peaks were observed on both observed file and the XRD pattern of (5% SCBA) has more intense peaks than (10% SCBA). C-S-H peaks indicate the pozzolanic reaction between $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ and amorphous

silica presented in SCBA. This additional hydration product C-S-H has the cementitious properties and it improves the compressive strength of concrete.

Fig 16 The XRD pattern of grade M-20 (95%OPC+5%SCBA) concrete crushes at curing age 28days

Fig 17 The XRD pattern of grade M-20 (90 %OPC+10 %SCBA) concrete crushes at curing age of 28days

Target Strength of Concrete

The target strength of the concrete mixture is defined as: Target Strength = $f_{ck} + 1.65\sigma$, where σ is the standard deviation and f_{ck} is the characteristic strength.

Target Strength of Concrete Grade M-15 (1:2:4) and M-20 (1:1.5:3)**For Grade M-15 (1:2:4)**

Target Strength, $f_t = f_{ck} + 1.65 \sigma$

$f_t = 15 + 1.65 \times 3.5$ (Standard Deviation for grade M-15 is 3.5)

$f_t = 20.775$ MPa

For Grade M-20 (1:1.5:3)

Target Strength, $f_t = f_{ck} + 1.65 \sigma$

$f_t = 20 + 1.65 \times 4$ (Standard Deviation for grade M-20 is 4)

$f_t = 26.6$ MPa

Density, Maximum load and Compressive Strength

The density, maximum load and compressive strength of all concrete cubes were measured and tested at Myanmar Engineering Society, MES Quality Control Laboratory, Compression Test of Concrete Specimens room, Hlaing University Campus, Hlaing Township, Yangon, Myanmar. The density was determined basically by measuring the weight, length, width and height of the sample concrete cubes. By observing the MES's result, it was found that the density, maximum load and compressive strength of both 5%SCBA(grade M-15 and M-20) concrete cubes are higher than that of OPC concrete and that of 10%SCBA (grade M-15) concrete is approximately equal to that of OPC concrete. It was also found that the compressive strength of 10% SCBA (grade M-20) has equal value that of OPC concrete. By comparing, the maximum load and compressive strength of 20%SCB, 30%SCBA and 40%SCBA concretes are less than that of OPC concrete. The maximum load and compressive strength were tested by 2000kN compression machine and the results were shown in table 5 and 6. The comparison of measureable compressive strength and target strength for grade M-15 and M-20 were shown in table 7 and 8. The density, maximum load and compressive strength of bar graphs were shown in fig 18-23.

Table 5 Density, Maximum Load and Compressive Strength of specimens (grade M-15;1:2:4 ; cement replacement by SCBA)

Specimen no.	Sample	Sample	Sample	Sample	Sample	Sample
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
	0%	5%	10%	20%	30%	40%
	SCBA	SCBA	SCBA	SCBA	SCBA	SCBA
Making on Specimen	15.12.15	20.1.16	4.7.16	4.7.16	24.7.16	24.7.16
Date of Test	12.1.16	18.2.16	1.8.16	1.8.16	22.8.16	22.8.16
Age(days)	28	28	28	28	28	28
Weight (kg)	7.66	7.05	7.38	7.48	7.17	7.04
Length(mm)	149.42	149.31	149.89	149.8	149.82	149.9
width(mm)	150.38	149.26	150	149.82	150	150.12
Height(mm)	151.93	140.64	149.8	150	151.34	151.34
Density(kg/m ³)	2243.83	2249.30	2191.19	2221.92	2108.16	2067.18
Maximum Load(kN)	495.65	519.16	477.82	364.53	254.58	188.57
Compressive Strength (N/mm ²)	22.56	23.30	21.25	16.25	11.33	8.38
(lb/in ²)	3272.06	3378.99	3082.61	2357.33	1643.16	1215.49

Fig 18 density of M-15 concrete cubes

Fig 19 maximum load of M-15 concrete cubes

Fig 20 compressive strength of M-15 concrete cubes

**Table 8 Density, Maximum Load and Compressive Strength of specimens
(grade M-20;1:1.5:3 ; cement replacement by SCBA)**

Fig 22 maximum load of M-20 concrete cubes

Specimen no.	Sample (1) 0% SCBA	Sample (2) 5% SCBA	Sample (3) 10% SCBA	Sample (4) 20% SCBA	Sample (5) 30% SCBA	Sample (6) 40% SCBA
Making on Specimen	3.10. 16	16.1.17	16.1.17	5.9. 16	5.9. 16	3.10. 16
Date of Test	31.10. 16	13.2. 17	13.2. 17	3.10. 16	3.10. 16	31.10. 16
Age(days)	28	28	28	28	28	28
Weight (kg)	7.78	7.33	7.35	7.48	7.32	7.14
Length(mm)	149.78	150.54	150.5	150.6	150.2	149.73
width(mm)	150.8	150.46	150.43	150.72	150.57	149.89
Height(mm)	150.45	150.38	150.38	150.39	150.21	150.17
Density (kg/m ³)	2289.58	2152	2158.87	2190.98	2154.84	2118.69
Maximum Load (kN)	772.74	835.93	782.35	469.77	311.54	242.65
Compressive Strength (N/mm ²)	34.23	36.91	34.56	20.70	13.78	10.81
(lb/in ²)	4964.44	5353.21	5012.42	3001.98	1998.13	1568.25

Fig 21 density of M-20 concrete cubes

Fig 22 maximum load of M-20 concrete cubes

Fig 23 compressive strength of M-20 concrete cubes

Fig 24 The photograph of MES’s certificate

Conclusion

Qualification of sugarcane bagasse ash in partial cement replacement in concrete has been studied. By observing the EDXRF analysis of SCBA and OPC, it was found that SCBA contain high amount of silica and second dominant elements were potassium and calcium. The elements contain in both SCBA and OPC were almost the same. By observing the XRD patterns of partial replacing cement by 5% and 10% SCBA in concrete crushes, grade M-20 , it was found that the hydration product, calcium silicate hydrate, C-S-H formed during the hydration of OPC and it was shown that the pozzolanic behavior of the SCBA. During mixing the ingredients of concrete with water, replacing cement by higher percent SCBA concrete paste required the more water. Adding more water to a concrete mix gives a weaker hardened concrete. The measured value of maximum load and compressive strength of both grade M-15 and M-20, 5% SCBA in blended concrete cubes were higher than that of (0% SCBA), OPC concrete and 10% SCBA in blended concrete cubes were approximated that of OPC concrete. The more requirement of w/c ratio causes decrease of the compressive strength. The replacement of up to 10% cement by SCBA could be effectively

used. Fineness of bagasse ash is also the important factor affecting the compressive strength of concrete.

Acknowledgements

I would like to thank Professor Dr May Myint Si, Head of Department of Physics, Dagon University, for her kind permission to carry out this work. I would like to thank Professor Dr Than Tun, Department of Physics, Dagon University, for her helpful advice to present this research.

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